

ISOLATION AND BIOLOGY TRAITS OF XYLELLA FASTIDIOSA ISOLATES RECOVERED IN APULIA

M. SAPONARI^{1*}, G. ALTAMURA¹, G. D'ATTOMA^{1,2}, C. DONGIOVANNI³, P. LA NOTTE¹,
L. SUSCA², O. POTERE², G. LOCONSOLE², S. ZICCA¹, M. MORELLI¹, F. PALMISANO³,
D. TAVANO¹, D. BOSCIA¹

¹CNR ISTITUTO PER LA PROTEZIONE SOSTENIBILE DELLE PIANTE UOS BARI (IPSP), SS BARI, 70126 BARI, ITALY.
²DIPARTIMENTO DI SCIENZE DEL SUOLO, DELLA PIANTA E DEGLI ALIMENTI (DI.S.S.P.A.) UNIVERSITÀ DEGLI STUDI DI BARI
ALDO MORO, 70126, BARI, ITALY.³CENTRO DI RICERCA, SPERIMENTAZIONE E FORMAZIONE IN AGRICOLTURA "BASILE
CARAMIA", LOCOROTONDO, BARI, ITALY.

***Corresponding author: maria.saponari@ipsp.cnr.it**

The isolation in pure culture of the *Xylella fastidiosa* is one of the critical steps for establishing comprehensive research programs aiming at investigating its host range, genomics and population genetics. An isolation campaign was started in Apulia in spring 2016 to collect isolates representing several foci in the infected demarcated area of Apulia (southern Italy) and different hosts. Axenic cultures were successfully established either using hardwood cuttings squeezed on BCYE medium (olive, oleander, myrtle-leaf milkwort, cherry, almond and laurel) or by plating dilutions of the PBS-extracts from leaves on PWG plates (oleander, cherry, myrtle-leaf milkwort and lavender). The isolates (approx. 50) so far recovered are preserved at -80°C in 50% glycerol and available for genomic and genetic studies. Evaluation of the pathogenicity and host specificity of the selected reference olive strain "De Donno" was started at the end of 2014 within the EFSA Pilot project NP.EFSA.ALPHA.2014.07, and further implemented within the first year of the project POnTE, with the specific objective of consolidating the knowledge on the susceptibility of grapes and stone fruits upon mechanical inoculations or exposure to naturally infected vectors. Indeed, the pathogenicity on olives was confirmed by inoculating a new set of plants of the susceptible variety "Cellina di Nardò". Although the inoculation procedure (three inoculum points per plant) and the growing conditions (at 24-28°C) need to be further optimized, the procedure so far adopted proved to be efficient for the successful infection and the symptom development in the susceptible hosts, i.e. olive and myrtle-leaf milkwort. Within the 2016 surveys for the identification of susceptible hosts in the infected area, several novel and hitherto unknown susceptible species to the CoDiRO strain have been reported, including typical essences of the "Macchia Mediterranea" and common weeds.